

Full Duplex Millimeter-Wave Cellular Networks: A Macroscopic Point-of-view

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Abstract—The synergy of full-duplex (FD) radio and millimeter-wave (mmWave) communications can be jointly beneficial, as FD can enhance the spectral efficiency of a point-to-point link, while the prominent properties of mmWave communications can mitigate the overall interference. However, the FD operation in the context of large-scale networks leads to an increased multi-user interference, imposing a trade-off between improving the average spectral efficiency and increasing the aggregate interference. Furthermore, although the increase of multi-user interference due to the FD operation is harmful for information decoding, it can be beneficial for energy harvesting, and hence, the trade-off between successful information decoding and average harvested energy emerges. Hence, in this article, we describe the application of stochastic geometry to model and design FD-enabled mmWave communications in the context of large-scale heterogeneous networks. Based on the proposed framework, we assess the performance of heterogeneous FD-mmWave cellular networks under two user location-based classifications, namely cell-center users (CCUs) and cell-edge users (CEUs), and evaluate the trade-offs imposed by the FD operation. Numerical results demonstrate that the half-duplex operation of the CEUs is preferable for achieving better network performance, in contrast to the CCUs for which FD operation is more efficient.

Index Terms—Full-duplex, millimeter-wave, heterogeneous networks, stochastic geometry.

I. INTRODUCTION

Future wireless networks, namely beyond fifth Generation (5G) and sixth Generation (6G), are expected to accommodate massive numbers of user equipments (UEs) with increasingly demanding spectral efficiency (SE) requirements. Aiming to address this demand, future wireless networks are envisioned as a synergy of several state-of-the-art techniques, such as full-duplex (FD) radio, heterogeneous network (HetNet) deployments and millimeter-wave (mmWave) communications [1]. FD radio refers to the simultaneous operation of both transmission and reception using non-orthogonal channels, which can potentially double the overall SE when compared to the conventional half-duplex (HD) networks [2]. Nevertheless, the non-orthogonal operation of an FD transceiver leads to self-interference (SI) between the output and the input antennas. Due to the short distance between the output and input antennas of a transceiver, the SI is much stronger than the received signal power from a remote transmit antenna, compromising the ability of a node

to decode the desired signal [1]. Hence, the FD technology has been previously considered as an infeasible approach. Fortunately, recent advances in antenna technology and signal processing have made a great leap forward in successfully mitigating the SI and therefore, made FD feasible [2].

The potential gains of the FD technology compared to the HD operation have been clarified by adopting information theoretic tools and by exploring the achievable rate regions [3]. Despite the maturity reached in the design of a small-scale networks, such as single-cell scenarios, a profound understanding of the role played by the FD operation in more complex networks deployments is however still elusive. In fact, the concept of FD radio in large-scale networks, such as multi-cell scenarios, triggers a non-trivial trade-off between spatial reuse and aggregate interference [2]. On the one hand, with the existence of simultaneous bidirectional data exchange within node pairs, more links per unit area can be active and can potentially lead to enhanced SE. Moreover, although the multi-user interference is characterized as the main degradation factor in conventional networks, it can be viewed as a useful aggregate energy signal that could be exploited for the harvesting purposes of low-powered devices, such as Internet-of-Things devices [4]. On the other hand, the additional amount of interference caused by a more aggressive access to the medium, decreases the probability of successfully retrieving information. Hence, the overall balance of the counter-posed effects introduced by the FD operation on large-scale networks need to be addressed. Furthermore, the investigation of a theoretical perspective is required in order to derive general design principles for future wireless networks.

This was the key motivating factor for introducing a powerful mathematical tool, namely stochastic geometry (SG). Specifically, SG consists of a branch of applied probability tools, which captures the random nature of large-scale networks and permits the analytical characterization of numerous performance metrics [5]. Since next-generation networks demand ultra-reliable connectivity and higher data rates, the evaluation of the coverage performance and the average SE is of paramount importance. Moreover, the vision of future wireless networks to support self-sustainable low-powered devices which harvest the ambient RF energy in order to power their operations, motivates the evaluation of the average RF harvested energy at a receiver within the network [6].

Several research works have examined the impact of self- and multi-user interference on the performance of large-scale FD-enabled systems, and numerous techniques have been developed aiming to mitigate the severe interference imposed by the FD operation. The authors in [7] illustrate the importance of highly-directional antennas in confining the aggregate interference as well as in passively suppress

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the SI. A hybrid HD/FD heterogeneous cellular network is considered in [8], where the authors demonstrated that an enhanced network throughput can be achieved by assigning different duplex modes for the different tiers. Similarly in [9], the authors considered a hybrid HD/FD multi-tier cellular network and highlighted that the maximum rate region of an FD link can be achieved by properly and opportunistically adopting HD and FD transmissions.

MmWave communication is considered as an indispensable part of both the fifth-generation and future wireless communications, owing to its vast available spectrum resources that can deliver multi-Gbps rates [10]. Nevertheless, the conventional time-division/frequency-division duplexing may reduce the effective capacity of mmWave communications [11]. Leveraging the concept of FD radio, the mmWave spectrum can be utilized more efficiently than before. Furthermore, due to the much shorter wavelengths of the mmWave signals, tens-to-hundreds of antenna elements can be integrated onto small-sized chips, thereby producing highly directional antennas [14]. Beyond boosting the network throughput through the high antenna gain, high directivity also enhances the spatial reuse, mitigates the interference, and assists in suppressing the SI in FD communications. Moreover, network densification through the heterogeneous deployment of base stations (BSs), can alleviate the severe path-loss attenuation of mmWave frequencies, by reducing the distance between the transmitter and the receiver. Thus, the co-design of FD radio and mmWave communications in the context of HetNets, is of paramount importance to mitigate the overwhelmingly multi-user interference by leveraging the outstanding properties of mmWave communications. The feasibility of FD radio in the context of mmWave communications was assessed in [11]. Recent studies focus on identifying the most beneficial mode of operation of an FD-enabled UE, depending on its location within a cell i.e., in the cell-center or in the cell-edge region, in the context of hybrid FD/HD mmWave HetNets [13].

The goal of this article is to assess the effect of FD radio on large-scale heterogeneous mmWave networks, and study the trade-offs imposed by the FD operation on fundamental network performance metrics. Initially, we discuss on how SG provides a better understanding of the large-scale networks, and shed light on the modeling and analysis of FD-enabled mmWave communications from a macroscopic point-of-view. Based on the proposed SG-based framework, the performance of large-scale heterogeneous FD-mmWave cellular networks is evaluated for two user location-based classifications, namely cell-center users (CCUs) and cell-edge users (CEUs). Motivated by the counter-posed effects introduced by the FD operation on large-scale networks, in this work, we evaluate the emerging trade-offs imposed between fundamental network performance metrics. We firstly reveal the trade-off between improving the average SE and increasing the aggregate network interference. Then, by considering the beneficial impact of the multi-user interference for EH, the trade-off between the successful information decoding and average harvested energy is highlighted. According to our results, FD operation is beneficial for the CCUs while HD operation is more advantageous for the CEUs.

Fig. 1: The impact of FD operation in large-scale networks. User 1 and User 5 operate in HD mode for the DL direction, User 2 and User 3 operate in HD mode for the UL direction, and User 4 operates in FD mode.

II. FD-MMWAVE COMMUNICATIONS: A MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Until recently, both the academia and the industry were extensively using the hexagonal grid model to study cellular networks [14]. Although such approach offers a flexible and reasonably useful model for representing well-planned homogeneous BS deployments, it leads to either intractable results which require massive Monte Carlo simulation [14]. Furthermore, due to the fluctuation of the demand across the service area, the BSs do not exactly follow a grid-based model. Therefore, the grid-based modeling assumption is violated and is considered too idealized. Moving to the current HetNet deployments, which are consisting of multiple tiers of BSs, the network topology evolves towards an irregular spatial deployment of nodes. Recently, the SG modeling approach has been adopted for large-scale HetNet deployments that captures the topological randomness in the network geometry and leads to tractable analytical results. In this case, the locations of the BSs are abstracted to a convenient point process (PP) which captures the spatial properties of the BSs. Among a plethora of PPs, the Poisson PP (PPP) is the most adopted process since it possesses the property of “complete spatial randomness”.

A. Network Modeling

Consider a heterogeneous FD-mmWave network consisting of $\mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, K\}$ tiers. The BSs in the k -th tier are independently distributed based on a PPP $\Phi_k \sim \text{PPP}(\lambda_k)$ and transmit with power P_k , where λ_k depicts the density of the BSs in a unit area. Users form another independent PPP Φ_u with spatial density $\lambda_u \gg \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \lambda_k$.

We assume that all BSs operate in FD mode, while all UEs are FD-capable. Specifically, a fraction δ^F of UEs operates in FD mode, while the rest operate in HD mode and can either serve for the downlink (DL) or uplink (UL) transmission with probabilities δ^D and δ^U , respectively. Fig. 1 demonstrates the impact of FD operation in a heterogeneous multi-cell network. Specifically, a two-cell network with multiple UEs in each cell is considered, where the active links are depicted with

solid blue lines and the interference signals with dashed red lines. For simplicity, Fig. 1 only demonstrates the interference observed by the UEs within cell 1. From Fig. 1, besides the inter-cell BS-to-UE interference and inter-cell UE-to-BS interference that already exists in the HD networks, the FD networks also experience inter-cell inter-BS interference and inter-cell inter-UE interference. Furthermore, the FD networks face intra-cell inter-UE interference as well as SI (I_{SI}). For the considered scenario where the UEs are FD-capable, additional interference is caused which are depicted with dotted green lines, and hence, the overall interference is further escalated.

B. Channel Model

All channels in the network are assumed to be subject to both large-scale path-loss effects and small-scale fading. Specifically, the large-scale path-loss follows an unbounded model based on the distance r between a transmitter and a receiver, which is equal to cr^{-a} , where $a > 2$ is the path-loss exponent and c is a constant that is determined by the carrier frequency and the reference distance. In the context of mmWave systems, where the LoS component is considered in the channel model, the small-scale fading follows a Nakagami distribution. This is motivated by the fact that the Nakagami- ν distribution has greater flexibility and accuracy in matching some experimental data than the Rayleigh, log-normal or Rice distributions [14]. Furthermore, the Nakagami- ν distribution is a generalized distribution which can model different fading environments, where Rayleigh and Rician distributions are its special cases [14]. Hence, the power of the channel fading is a Gamma random variable with shape parameter ν and scale parameter $1/\nu$. Regarding the SI channel, many effective SI cancellation techniques have been proposed, aiming to suppress the SI signal below the receiver's noise floor [3]. However, perfect SI cancellation is practically infeasible, and therefore, the FD-enabled transceivers are considered to utilize imperfect cancellation mechanisms [15]. The residual SI channel coefficient follows a Nakagami distribution with parameters (μ, σ_{SI}^2) , where $1/\sigma_{SI}^2$ represents the efficiency of a FD-enabled transceiver in cancelling the SI. Hence, the power gain of the residual SI channel follows a Gamma distribution [15] with mean μ and variance σ_{SI}^2/μ . Due to the ultra-dense deployment of BSs, the considered network deployment operates in the interference-limited region [13] i.e., thermal noise is neglected.

C. MmWave features Model

The small wavelength of the mmWave signals allows the fabrication of smaller antenna elements and the placement of tens or even hundreds of them at the transceivers [10]. By leveraging the large-scale directional antenna arrays, massive array gains and highly directional beams can be achieved. The main concept of directional antenna arrays is to focus the transmitter's energy towards certain directions, while suppressing it in the direction of the unintended receivers [10]. Hence, the utilization of directional antennas provides to the network an increased coverage performance and the interference caused by the nearby sources is significantly

reduced. To facilitate the analysis, the actual beam pattern is approximated by a sectorized model where constant directivity gains are assumed for both the main lobe and side lobes. The approximation of sectorized patterns makes it possible to characterize complex beamforming patterns with their key features: main-lobe beamwidth $\theta \in (0, 2\pi]$, main-lobe gain M (dB), and side-lobe gain m (dB), where $M > m$.

Another important feature of the mmWave signals is their sensitivity to blockage effects [11]. In particular, the short wavelength of the mmWave frequency band incur a greater attenuation on the multi-path effects e.g., diffraction and higher-order reflection, and therefore, the penetration loss of the mmWave signals is significantly higher than the sub-6 GHz counterpart [10]. Hence, in contrast to conventional sub-6 GHz cellular networks, mmWave systems mainly depend on the line-of-sight (LoS) transmissions in order to achieve high data-rate performance. For modeling the blockage effects, we leverage tools from random shape theory that models the locations of the blockages as a stationary process of objects on the plane \mathbb{R}^2 . Then, the LoS probability function of a link is expressed as a function of the link length r , and is equal to $p(r) = \exp(-\beta r)$, where β is a non-negative blockage constant that models the blockage density and their characteristics [10]. Given that the channel gain of the non-LoS links is greatly smaller than that of the LoS links [10], and all UEs observe several LoS BSs due to the extremely dense HetNet deployments, the effect of non-LoS links can be neglected without sacrificing accuracy. Therefore, the LoS BSs that belong in the k -th tier of a HetNet form a PPP Φ_k^L with non-homogeneous density $\lambda_k \exp(-\beta r)$, based on the thinning property of the PPPs [5].

D. Power Allocation Model

As battery-powered devices possess insufficient power resources, the efficient power distribution for the UL direction is a critical aspect of next-generation networks. Hence, a distance-proportional fractional power control mechanism is utilized by all UEs, aiming to counterbalance the large-scale path-loss and achieve an average received signal power at their serving BSs equal to a threshold ρ . Specifically, for a UE of which the serving BS is located at distance r and is experiencing a large-scale path-loss equal to cr^{-a} , its transmitted signal power is adapted to $\rho c^{-1} r^{a\epsilon}$, where $0 \leq \epsilon \leq 1$. According to the UL power control mechanism adopted in the Long-Term-Evolution [13] standard, the transmission power assigned to a UE is equal to $P_u(r) = \min\{\rho c^{-1} r^{a\epsilon}, P_m\}$, where the UEs transmit at maximum power P_m when the fully inversion of the path loss is infeasible.

E. Location-based Classification

The achieved performance of a UE is strongly correlated with the UE's location within the network. Particularly, a UE located nearby its serving BS is confronting small path-loss attenuation, and therefore the signal power received by the serving BS is substantially higher than the observed interference. Nevertheless, as the distance between the UE and the serving BS increases, the path-loss attenuation becomes

Fig. 2: The Voronoi tessellation of a two-tier FD-mmWave cellular network, where the macro-BSs, the micro-BSs and the UEs are represented by circles, rectangles and triangles, respectively. Red and blue areas represent the cell-edge regions of macro-tier and micro-tier, respectively.

more intense, where beyond a critical point the UE receives weaker signal power from the serving BS compared to the observed interference. Hence, each communication cell can be divided into two disjoint sub-regions based on the network topology, namely 1) cell-center region, in which the serving BS is significantly closer than the dominant interfering BS, and 2) cell-edge region, in which the distances from the serving BS and the dominant interfering BS are relatively equal. A UE is classified as cell-edge user (CEU) with respect to the k -th tier, if $\frac{R_s}{R_d} > \zeta$, otherwise as cell-center user (CCU), where R_s and R_d denote the distances of the first and the second closest LoS BSs and $\zeta \in [0, 1]$ is a predefined fraction. Fig. 2 demonstrates a FD-mmWave cellular network consisting of a macro-tier BS network and a denser micro-tier BS network for different values of $\zeta = \{0.5, 0.7\}$. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the UEs can be classified into one of the following disjoint regions: 1) cell-center for both tiers, 2) cell-edge for both tiers, 3) cell-center for the macro-tier and cell-edge for the micro-tier, and 4) cell-edge for the macro-tier and the cell-center for the micro-tier. Furthermore, the monotonic decrease of both cell-edge regions with the increase of ζ is illustrated in Fig. 2. For instance, for the case where $\zeta = 0.5$, *User 1* is located in the cell-center region of the macro-tier and in the cell-edge region of the micro-tier, while for the case where $\zeta = 0.7$, *User 1* is classified in the cell-center region of both tiers.

III. TRADE-OFF RELATED TO FD OPERATION IN HETEROGENEOUS FD-MMWAVE NETWORKS

In this section, we evaluate the performance of FD radio in heterogeneous mmWave cellular networks from a macroscopic point-of-view. Without loss of generality and following Slivnyak's theorem [5], we execute the analysis for a typical UE located at the origin but the results hold for all UEs of the network.

Regarding the cell association for both the DL and UL transmissions, weighted path-loss user association criteria are adopted, where an FD UE can be served either by a single FD BS for both the DL and UL transmissions or by two

different BSs for the DL and UL transmissions [7]. For the DL direction, we adopt a received signal strength (RSS)-based association scheme i.e., a UE is associated with the LoS BS that provides the strongest received power, while for the UL direction, we adopt a distance-based association scheme i.e., a UE is associated with the closest LoS BS. The investigated performance metrics can then be described as follows.

1) *Coverage Performance*: The DL and UL coverage performance of a network can be described as the probability that an arbitrary receiver can successfully decode the received signal power for the DL and UL transmission, respectively. This performance can be mathematically described with the probability $\mathbb{P}[\gamma^\ell > \tau]$, where τ is the minimum required threshold of the observed signal-to-interference ratio (SIR) at the typical receiver for the ℓ transmission, denoted as γ^ℓ , where $\ell \in \{\text{DL}, \text{UL}\}$. Based on the system model described in earlier Section and the aforementioned discussion, the DL and the UL SIR for the typical receiver (i.e., a UE or a BS), can be expressed as follows

$$\gamma^{\text{DL}} = \frac{M^2 \frac{cP_i}{\|x_D\|^\alpha} h_0}{I^D + \mathbb{1}_{\text{FD}} I_{\text{SI}}^D}, \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma^{\text{UL}} = \frac{M^2 \frac{cP_u}{\|x_U\|^\alpha} \tilde{h}_0}{I^U + I_{\text{SI}}^U}, \quad (1)$$

respectively, where $\|x_D\|$ and $\|x_U\|$ are the Euclidean distance of the serving BSs located at $x_D \in \Phi_i^L$ for the DL and $x_U \in \Phi_j^L$ for the UL transmission, respectively; I^D and I^U depict the interferences experienced by a UE in the DL and UL transmissions, respectively; h_0 and \tilde{h}_0 are the channel fading between the typical receiver and its serving transmitter for the DL and UL transmissions, respectively; $\mathbb{1}_{\text{FD}}$ is the indicator function for the event “the typical UE is FD-capable”, and the residual SI observed at the FD UEs and the BSs are denoted as I_{SI}^D and I_{SI}^U , respectively. Efficient analytical expressions to compute the SIR distribution can be found in prior work [13].

2) *Average Spectral Efficiency*: An equally important performance metric is the average SE that refers to the information rate that can be transmitted over a given bandwidth for the considered system model. Specifically, the average SE determines the volume of concurrently supported UEs in a limited RF bandwidth within a defined geographic area.

Fig. 3: DL coverage performance versus SE.

In order to analyze and obtain analytical expressions for the average SE of the typical receiver in the context of the presented heterogeneous FD-mmWave network, we utilize the SIR distribution framework obtained in the above sub-section III-1.

3) *Average RF Harvested Energy*: It is assumed that the BSs have a continuous power supply, while all UEs are solely powered by the harvested RF energy in order to power their operations. Specifically, we assume that each UE has simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT) capabilities and so it can decode the information and also harvest energy from the received signal simultaneously. We consider a power-splitting method for the SWIPT technique. Specifically, the received signal is divided into two parts i.e., one is converted to a baseband signal for information decoding and the other is directed to the rectenna for EH. Let $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ denote the power-splitting parameter for each UE i.e., $100\alpha\%$ of the received power is used for decoding while the remaining power, denoted as ω , is inputted to the EH circuit. Then, the harvested energy can be written as a function of ω i.e., $\mathcal{E} = g(\omega)$, where $g: \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ is a non-decreasing non-linear function of its argument [16]. To facilitate the analysis, a piecewise linear model is considered, which is endowed with three main factors that strongly limit the performance of a harvesting receiver, namely (i) its sensitivity level, $\underline{\omega}$, which is the minimum RF input power required for EH, (ii) its saturation level, $\bar{\omega}$, which refers to a linear transition region and is the RF input power for which the diode of the rectenna begins to operate in the breakdown region, and (iii) the energy efficiency $\eta \in [0, 1]$, which is assumed to be constant. Hence, we can express the harvested energy as follows [16]

$$\mathcal{E} = \begin{cases} 0 & \omega < \underline{\omega}, \\ \eta\omega & \underline{\omega} \leq \omega < \bar{\omega}, \\ \eta\bar{\omega} & \omega \geq \bar{\omega}, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

and the average EH can be calculated as $\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{E}]$.

The incurred trade-offs between the aforementioned performance metrics for the heterogeneous FD-mmWave cellular networks are illustrated in the following sections, where the simulation parameters are described in Table I. It is important

Fig. 4: UL coverage performance versus SE.

to mention here that, the use of different values will lead to a shifted network performance, but with the same conclusions.

A. Coverage and Average Spectral Efficiency Trade-off

Figs. 3 and 4 show the trade-off between the average SE and the DL and UL coverage performance with respect to the fraction of FD UEs, respectively. We can first observe that the FD operation slightly increases the coverage performance for the cases CE, EC, and EE, when the portion of FD UEs is small. This was expected as the increased probability of UEs operating in FD mode tends to convert the dominant interfering BS to a serving BS, resulting in an enhanced SIR as the observed interference is significantly reduced. Nevertheless, the network performance diminishes when the portion of FD UEs exceeds a critical point, as the increased number of active FD UEs leads to an escalated network interference. We can also observe the significant negative effect imposed by the increased number of FD UEs on the DL coverage performance of EC and EE cases, where UEs are more susceptible to interference variations as a result of their short distances from the interfering BSs. In contrast, by increasing the number of FD UEs for the CC and CE cases, the DL coverage performance is insignificantly reduced. On the contrary, the boosted number of transmissions in both DL and UL directions leads to a significantly enhanced average spectral performance. As expected, the CC and CE scenarios attain higher average spectral performance gains in respect of the EC and EE scenarios.

Similar behaviour and conclusions can be observed in Fig. 4. Nevertheless, for a given fraction of FD UEs, the coverage performance for the DL direction exceeds the corresponding performance for the UL direction. Another important observation is that, the degradation of the coverage performance with the increase of the number of FD UEs is more pronounced for the UL direction compared to that for the DL direction. Both of these observations rely on the adoption of different user association schemes for the DL and UL directions [13].

B. Coverage and Average RF Harvested Energy Trade-off

The trade-off between the average harvested energy and the DL coverage performance is illustrated in Fig. 5, for different

TABLE I: Summary of Notations

Description	Value
Total number of network tiers	$K = 2$
Density and transmit power of BSs	$\lambda_1 = 31$ BSs/km ² , $\lambda_2 = 93$ BSs/km ² , $P_1 = 25$ dB, and $P_2 = 15$ dB
Classification and decoding threshold	$\zeta = 0.7$, $\tau = 0$ dB
User Classifications	1) CCU for both tiers (scenario "CC"), 2) CCU for the macro-tier and CEU for the micro-tier (scenario "CE"), 3) CEU for the macro-tier and CCU for the micro-tier (scenario "EC"), and 4) CEU for both tiers (scenario "EE")
User's operation mode	$\delta^D = 0.5$ and $\delta^U = 0.5$ [13]
Power control scheme	$\rho = -40$ dB, $\epsilon = 0.9$, and $P_m = 5$ dB [2]
Small-scale and large-scale fading	$a = 4$, $c = 60$ dB and $\nu = 2$ [13]
Residual SI channel	$\mu = 4$ and $\sigma_{SI} = -40$ dB [7]
Sectorized antenna and blockage model	$M = 10$ dB, $m = -10$ dB, $\theta = \pi/6$, and $\beta = 0.03$ [13]
Harvester circuit	$\underline{\omega} = -22$ dBm, $\bar{\omega} = -4.8$ dBm, and $\eta = 0.7$ [16]

Fig. 5: DL coverage performance versus RF EH.

power-splitting parameters $\alpha = \{0.25, 0.75\}$, and different fractions of FD UEs $\delta^F \in [0, 1]$. Similar as in Figs. 3 and 4, each point in the curves depicts the trade-off between the two performance metrics for a given fraction of FD UEs. As already observed in Figs. 3 and 4, the coverage performance reduces with the increase of the number of FD UEs due to the increased multi-user interference. Moreover, we can easily observe, that the average harvested energy at a SWIPT-enabled UE is improved with the raise of the fraction of FD UEs. This was expected, since by increasing the number of FD UEs, more and more links become active within the network, and consequently, the received RF ambient energy at the typical UE's rectenna escalates. Another important observation is that, at low fraction of FD UEs, the average RF harvested energy of UEs located within the center region of a communication cell is larger compared with that of the UEs within the cell-edge region. This was expected, since the incident RF energy is dominated by the received signal power from the serving BS. However, by further increasing the fraction of FD UEs, the cell-edge UEs observe a significantly higher inter-cell interference compared with that observed at the cell-center UEs, and consequently the incident RF energy at their rectenna is larger with the cost of approximately zero coverage performance. Finally, it is obvious that by allocating a larger fraction of received power for EH leads to an improved average RF harvested energy.

IV. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

The SG-based analysis will become increasingly relevant for the complex wireless networks that will emerge in the era of B5G and 6G systems. This article establishes an analytical framework for the macroscopic analysis of heterogeneous FD-mmWave networks, and the results provide useful insights on the trade-offs imposed by the FD operation between key performance metrics. However, there still exists demanding challenges to address, which are listed below.

Three-dimensional modeling: In real-world network scenarios, the heights of BSs, blockages, or even UEs may have non-negligible impacts on the system performance. In particular, the macro-BSs, which are mainly tower-mounted, are more likely to establish a LoS link towards the UEs, since their higher height contributes in avoiding the blockages within the network area. Furthermore, as an emerging research topic, the use of FD-enabled aerial small-cells can significantly enhance the network performance, owing to the LoS air-to-ground links. On the other hand, high-rise buildings can potentially block all the LoS links between a UE and a BS, leading to a significant reduction in the network performance.

Temporal and Spatial Correlation: The majority of works with SG rely on a few assumptions that may not accurately hold in practical networks. The most important assumption refers to the random deployment of BSs, which are depicted as points of a homogeneous PPP, neglecting the temporal and spatial correlations. Despite the tractability offered by such assumption, in many practical networks, the locations of the macro-BSs are determined to alleviate the interference or extend the coverage region, and therefore there exists a form of repulsion among the network's nodes. Moreover, the locations of the small-cell BSs aim to complement the coverage and the capacity of the cellular networks at user hotspots. In order to emulate all nodes configurations that appear in heterogeneous FD-mmWave networks (either repulsive for macro-BSs or attractive for small-cell BSs), more general point processes need to be considered, such as Ginibre point process, Poisson cluster process, etc.

Synergy of SG and machine learning: Another interesting future direction is to integrate machine learning with SG. Specifically, the concept of SG can be embedded as a class of hypothesis in the learning process of the machine learning. A demonstrative case is the class of problems known as

the subset selection problems, where an optimal subset must be selected from a baseline set. Moreover, the synergy of SG and machine learning will also play an essential role in the employment of FD radio specifically in SI cancellation process. By using machine learning tools, the non-linearities imposed at a FD transceiver can be further compensated in order to generate more reliable SI cancellation signals. Furthermore, by utilizing the concept of machine learning, the severe multi-user interference can be alleviated by addressing a wide class of resource management problems, such as power control, link scheduling, UEs' mode of operation (e.g. FD, DL or UL), antenna directionality design, etc.

V. CONCLUSION

In this article, we argued that SG provides a rigorous approach to model, analyze and design large-scale heterogeneous FD-mmWave cellular networks. Specifically, we described how to apply SG to model and quantify coverage probability, average SE and average RF harvested energy for different location-based classifications of the UEs. Moreover, for each user classification, the trade-offs imposed by the FD operation of UEs between the considered metrics were shown and discussed. Our study reveals that HD is beneficial for CEUs since it offers better coverage performance and an adequate RF harvested energy. On the contrary, FD provides a significantly larger average SE and RF harvested energy to CCUs, with the cost of a slightly reduced coverage performance. Overall, we foresee that the FD radio will be an enabling technology for the upcoming B5G/6G networks with the potential to greatly improve many aspects of wireless networks such as the SE, RF harvested energy, etc.

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Fig. 6: The impact of FD operation in large-scale networks. User 1 and User 5 operate in HD mode for the DL direction, User 2 and User 3 operate in HD mode for the UL direction, and User 4 operates in FD mode.

Fig. 7: The Voronoi tessellation of a two-tier FD-mmWave cellular network, where the macro-BSs, the micro-BSs and the users are represented by circles, rectangles and triangles, respectively. Red and blue areas represent the cell-edge regions of macro-tier and micro-tier, respectively.

Fig. 8: DL coverage performance versus SE.

Fig. 9: UL coverage performance versus SE.

Fig. 10: DL coverage performance versus RF EH.